

IMPROVING THE USE OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN ENSURING THE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE OF THE ENTERPRISE

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Leading research institutes around the world are conducting extensive research on improving the use of marketing strategies to ensure competitive advantage for enterprises. In particular, the Ehrenberg-Bass Institute for Marketing Science in Australia is conducting research aimed at determining the impact of marketing investments on real competitive advantage by studying the empirical effectiveness of marketing strategies, the laws of brand growth and consumer behavior based on statistical data. The Academy of Marketing Science (AMS), one of the world's leading academic centers, coordinates research that provides in-depth scientific analysis of marketing strategies, market competition and consumer relations, and presents global statistical conclusions through high-impact scientific publications. The Institute for Market-oriented Management (IMU), operating in Europe, studies the impact of marketing strategies on corporate efficiency and competitiveness using real companies. These cases are considered priority areas of research for the effective use of marketing strategies to ensure competitive advantage for enterprises and for determining strategic opportunities for their implementation.

As a result of expert analysis from the point of view of competitive factors, the activities of "Parkent Samo" LLC are characterized by the following aspects. Service quality is rated low at 2 points, which indicates the need to increase service standards at this enterprise. Brand recognition and consumer loyalty are rated between 2 and 3 points, which indicates a weak marketing position of the enterprise in the market. There is no use of digital marketing tools, innovative activities and technological investments. Sales channels are carried out only offline, which limits the scope of services. This situation causes the low level of competitiveness of "Parkent Samo" LLC. The strength of the enterprise is the number of customer segments of 150 customers, but the lack of a mechanism for expanding this customer base through digital marketing weakens its competitive advantage.

A systematic model based on the concept of consumer-oriented marketing is presented in the formation of the enterprise's competitive advantage. It justifies the need to formulate the enterprise's marketing strategy with the needs and values of the consumer at the center.

To increase the competitiveness of enterprises, a consumer-oriented approach should be at the center of marketing activities. This approach is based on the marketing mix (4P) model developed by P. Kotler and the concept of customer value. This conceptual model scientifically substantiates the mechanism for managing marketing elements in a single system in forming the competitive advantage of an enterprise.

F. Kotler's approach interprets marketing strategies not only as a means of selling products, but also as a system for managing the value created for the consumer. In his opinion, competitive advantage is not simply the result of production efficiency or pricing policy, but also the ability of an enterprise to consistently offer high value to the customer. In this regard, Kotler interprets marketing as a strategic management system that ensures the competitiveness of an enterprise.

Also, in his subsequent research, F. Kotler put forward the ideas of relationship-based marketing and social marketing concepts, proposing to strengthen competitive advantage through long-term customer relationships, social responsibility and brand credibility.

The practical significance of this approach is that it allows enterprises to achieve the following results:

- increase consumer loyalty;
- form a positive brand image of the enterprise in the market;
- effectively allocate marketing resources;
- combine profitability with customer value;
- maintain a stable market share by differentiating from competitors

The research work developed a conceptual model for marketing management of a small business enterprise, which is based on the principles of relationship-based marketing and is based on the SOSTAC methodology proposed by P.R. Smith. Within the framework of this approach, marketing management in a small business enterprise includes an analysis of market opportunities, assessment of the internal and external environment, strategic and tactical planning, implementation of marketing activities and their control. The main content of the model is reflected in the focus on creating and developing value in cooperation with business customers. This ensures mutually beneficial cooperation between the parties, strengthening trusting relationships and achieving the strategic goals of the enterprise in the long term.

In order to assess the effectiveness of relationship marketing, the authors proposed a system of indicators based on measuring the satisfaction indices of

values for the elements of the 4R relationship marketing complex. These indicators allow us to quantitatively assess the level of achievement of the goals of the implementation of each model element and determine the effectiveness of marketing communications of the enterprise with business consumers.

A systematic model based on the concept of consumer-oriented marketing was developed to form the competitive advantage of the enterprise. It justifies the need to formulate the enterprise's marketing strategy with the needs and values of the consumer in the center. The process of ensuring competitiveness begins with an analysis of external environmental factors. Factors such as economic conditions, social values, technological developments, and market competition determine consumer needs and expectations. On this basis, we believe that a company should reshape its marketing strategy in accordance with the consumer's value system.

References:

1. Philip Kotler, Gary Armstrong, Sridhar Balasubramanian (2024) Principles of Marketing, Global Edition 19th Edition, 768 p.;
2. Saura J. R., Palacios-Marqués D., Ribeiro-Soriano D. Digital marketing in SMEs via data-driven strategies: Reviewing the current state of research //Journal of Small Business Management. – 2021. – C. 1-36.;
3. Sufian A. et al. The impact of social media marketing on sales performance of small online business //European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – T. 7. – №. 3. – C. 922-940.;
4. Kano K. et al. Implications of digital marketing strategy the competitive advantages of small businesses in indonesia //Starturreneur Bisnis Digital (SABDA Journal). – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 44-62.

